

THE IMPACT OF IT ON PEOPLE'S LIVE.

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Annotation: Information Technology has been a big part of our lives for quite a while now but only recently has it truly been felt in the developing world, of which Nigeria is one, however technology is a variety of different things not just the internet. Technology can be found anywhere, for instance, living room, school, on the street and even in parks. Technology can be found absolutely anywhere and as it has its direct impact on our works and social life.

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Technology has always been a part of our lives, even when we didn't know it. Now that technology is more integrated into our daily routines, do you find yourself wondering how much time you spend on your device? Does it feel like the world around you disappears when you are attached to your screen? You are not alone. We all have the same questions about the role of technology in our lives and what it means for us as people.

A huge part of technology is dependent on an internet connection. If you get an ISP like Spectrum internet, you get access to one of the best internet connections that offer high internet speed. The Internet can have a positive impact on your life if you use it in a positive way.

New technology, new applications, and new methods of interacting with the world are all around us. From driverless cars to robots that can cook meals, there's no denying that our lives are changing at an increasingly rapid pace. How does this affect our society? And how do we go about adjusting to these changes? We are highlighting the impact of technology on our lives in some ways.

Use of social media

Social media is a great way to stay connected with friends and family as well as share your knowledge and expertise with others.

It's more than that, though. It's also a powerful marketing tool that will help you connect with your current and future customers. There are hundreds of social media sites out there – Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Google+, Instagram, Pinterest, and so on – which means there's no shortage of opportunities to put your content in front of new people.

In business, technology has a major role to play in our lives today. It is a tool which has made our lives so much easier.

Technological advances have increased the scope of our jobs. More than ever before, we are faced with many choices in terms of how to do things. Technology has made it possible for us to work in various fields at the same time.

Technology is divided into two different types. The first is that which we use everyday – computers. The second is that which has been developed over time – the computer itself.

We may think of technology in terms of computers when discussing its impact on our lives, but even more so in terms of the impact of technology on people's jobs and lives. In both cases, the impact of technology on people is great.

Computer technology has brought about the evolution of every industry. It allows us to do everything we did before, in much more convenient ways. When you go to your office, you can use a computer, which not only helps you work, but also saves you money by eliminating the need for an expensive office. You can even save money by making your own personal computer and using it on your own time. This makes it possible for anyone to work from home – no longer does one have to commute.

Other technological advances have resulted in new fields of study. This has meant that we are better equipped than we were previously. We have the ability to do more with less. For example, if we think about the field of medicine, we see that medical technology has resulted in cures for almost all major illnesses, as well as treatments that can help us to survive the common cold. This kind of technology has created the need for nurses, doctors, surgeons, therapists, pharmacists, doctors of all sorts, and so forth.

All of today's technology has resulted in a much higher standard of living. There has been a massive increase in the number of available jobs and the standards of these jobs have improved drastically. We now have medical equipment which makes it possible to diagnose illnesses and give proper treatment to those who need it, without having to rely on expensive doctor's offices and clinics.

All of this technology has made life a lot easier for people, but there is a downside. Some people believe that technology has left us lacking some of the finer things of human relationships. This may be true for some people, but it certainly isn't true for the majority.

Technology has given us the ability to communicate with other people. However, we tend to underestimate how much our own communication skills improve when we use the technology. We can talk to others in person, send them emails, and make phone calls in a language they can understand – and in some cases we can learn to write them by reading a message or by using a software tool.

Technology has also allowed us to socialize with people far away from our homes. There is now email and instant messaging, which allow people to correspond and share their thoughts with others in a way that was previously impossible. People can make friends with others in other countries through the internet technology available today. This has led to the growth of international relations which is beneficial to everyone.

Computer games are a big part of our lives, which is another reason why people feel the need to communicate through technology. These games allow us to interact with our friends, family, and colleagues. The internet is also a major source of entertainment for many people. We can play games on our computers in the comfort of our homes and communicate with others across the world through the internet.

The benefits of technology on people's lives have resulted in an overall improvement in all aspects of life. It has made us more self-sufficient, gives us more options, and allows us to live more fulfilled and meaningful lives

Impact of technology on education

Technology has improved the quality of education and learning. The information available to students and teachers is an order of magnitude larger than it was just a decade ago.

The availability of resources and content has led to a boom in self-directed education or DIY education.

The internet is full of resources for those who wish to develop knowledge on their own. A quick Google search will turn up thousands of free resources for subjects such as math, science, history, and language. These resources are often created by people with a passion for the subject matter that they're teaching rather than teachers who are fulfilling requirements. Technology assists students to learn in a better way.

References:

- [1] Rouse, Margaret, "Information Technology (IT)", TechTarget [online] <<http://searchdatacenter.techtarget.com/definition/IT> > [Viewed 06/02/2018]
- [2] "IT Definition" Cambridge International Dictionary of English <<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/information-technology>> [Viewed 06/02/2018]
- [3] "Information Technology", encyclopedia.com [online] <<http://www.encyclopedia.com/science-and-technology/computers-and-electrical-engineering/computers-and-computing/information-1>> [Viewed 06/02/2018]

- [4] ROOS, DAVE, “How Information Technology Works”[Online]
<<https://money.howstuffworks.com/how-information-technology-works.htm>> [Viewed 07/02/2018]
- [5] Kenneth, I.Shine, “Impact of information technology on medicine”,
Elsevier [Online],
<<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0160791X96000048#!>> [Viewed 07/02/2018]

